

Supplementary Information:

Mathematical Proof

Guaranteed State of Charge Probability

Definition 1 (Guaranteed State of Charge Probability (GSCP)) *For a stochastic power queuing system, with a probabilistic upper bounded power demand process $E_A \sim \langle \epsilon_A^u, \alpha_A \rangle$ and probabilistic lower bounded power supply process $E_S \sim \langle \epsilon_S^l, \beta_S \rangle$, then for all $(t \in T : t \geq 0)$ and all $\gamma \geq 0$, given a maximum capacity C of the ESS, the amount of stored $e_{ESS}(t, C_{ESS})$ in the ESS is bounded by:*

$$GSCP(t, C_{ESS}) = P\{e_{ESS}(t, C_{ESS}) \geq \gamma\} \geq 1 - \epsilon_A^u \otimes \epsilon_S^l (C_{ESS} - \gamma - \sup_{0 \leq s \leq t} \{\alpha_A(s) - \beta_S(s)\}) \quad (14)$$

Proof Fix $t > 0$, then from Equations (7) and (11) it holds, that:

$$\begin{aligned} P\{e_{ESS}(t, C_{ESS}) \geq \gamma\} &= P\left\{\sup_{0 \leq u \leq t} \left(\inf_{u \leq s \leq t} (E_S(s, t) - E_A(s, t) + C_{ESS}, \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. E_S(u, t) - E_A(u, t) + C_{ESS} - C(u))\right) \geq \gamma\right\} \\ &= P\left\{C_{ESS} + \sup_{0 \leq u \leq t} \left(\inf_{u \leq s \leq t} (E_S(s, t) - E_A(s, t), \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. E_S(u, t) - E_A(u, t) - C(u))\right) \geq \gamma\right\} \\ &= P\left\{C_{ESS} + \sup_{0 \leq u \leq t} \left(-\sup_{u \leq s \leq t} (E_A(s, t) - E_S(s, t), \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. E_A(u, t) - E_S(u, t) + C(u))\right) \geq \gamma\right\} \\ &= P\left\{C_{ESS} - \inf_{0 \leq u \leq t} \left(\sup_{u \leq s \leq t} (E_A(s, t) - E_S(s, t), \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. E_A(u, t) - E_S(u, t) + C(u))\right) \geq \gamma\right\} \\ &= P\left\{\inf_{0 \leq u \leq t} \left(\sup_{u \leq s \leq t} (E_A(s, t) - E_S(s, t), \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. E_A(u, t) - E_S(u, t) + C(u))\right) \leq C_{ESS} - \gamma\right\} \\ &= 1 - P\left\{\inf_{0 \leq u \leq t} \left(\sup_{u \leq s \leq t} (E_A(s, t) - E_S(s, t), \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. E_A(u, t) - E_S(u, t) + C(u))\right) > C_{ESS} - \gamma\right\} \end{aligned}$$

Then the right-hand side of the probability can be bounded, using the representation of the actual storage capacity by the process $C(t) = C_{ESS} \forall t > 0$ and $C(t) = 0$ for $t = 0$ [7], as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
C_{ESS} - \gamma &< \inf_{0 \leq u \leq t} \left(\sup_{u \leq s \leq t} (E_A(s, t) - E_S(s, t), E_A(u, t) - E_S(u, t) + C(u)) \right) \\
&\leq \sup_{0 \leq s \leq t} (E_A(s, t) - E_S(s, t), E_A(0, t) - E_S(0, t) + C(0)) \\
&\leq \sup_{0 \leq s \leq t} (E_A(s, t) - E_S(s, t)) \\
&\leq \sup_{0 \leq s \leq t} (E_A(s, t) + \alpha_A(t-s) - \alpha_A(t-s) + \beta_S(t-s) - \beta_S(t-s) - E_S(s, t)) \\
&\leq \sup_{0 \leq s \leq t} (E_A(s, t) - \alpha_A(t-s)) + \sup_{0 \leq s \leq t} (\beta_S(t-s) - E_S(s, t)) \\
&\quad + \sup_{0 \leq s \leq t} (\alpha_A(s) - \beta_S(s))
\end{aligned}$$

By accounting for the Definition of the [Stochastic Energy Process](#):

$$P\left\{ \sup_{0 \leq s \leq t} \{(E_A(s, t) - \alpha_A(t-s))\} > x \right\} \leq \epsilon_A^u(x)$$

$$P\left\{ \sup_{0 \leq s \leq t} \{\beta_S(t-s) - E_S(s, t)\} > x \right\} \leq \epsilon_S^l(x)$$

and Equation (4) and the properties of the [\(min, +\)-convolution](#) its is proven, that:

$$\begin{aligned}
P\{e_{ESS}(t, C_{ESS}) \geq \gamma\} &= 1 - P\left\{ \inf_{0 \leq u \leq t} \left(\sup_{u \leq s \leq t} (E_A(s, t) - E_S(s, t), \right. \right. \\
&\quad \left. \left. E_A(u, t) - E_S(u, t) + C(u)) \right) > C_{ESS} - \gamma \right\} \\
&\geq 1 - \epsilon_A^u \otimes \epsilon_S^l(C_{ESS} - \gamma - \sup_{0 \leq s \leq t} \{\alpha_A(s) - \beta_S(s)\})
\end{aligned}$$

Thereby the random processes $E_S(t)$ and $E_A(t)$ are not required to be necessarily independent random variables. \square

Guaranteed Power Service Probability

Definition 2 (Guaranteed Power Service Probability (GPSP)) *For a stochastic power queuing system, with a probabilistic upper bounded power demand process $E_A \sim \langle \epsilon_A^u, \alpha_A \rangle$ and a probabilistic lower bounded power supply process $S \sim \langle \epsilon_S^l, \beta_S \rangle$, the unserved demand $E_L(t, C_{ESS})$ is bounded by:*

$$GPSP(t, C_{ESS}) = P\{E_L(t, C_{ESS}) \leq \lambda\} \geq 1 - \epsilon_A^u \otimes \epsilon_S^l (\lambda + C_{ESS} - \sup_{0 \leq s \leq t} \{\alpha_A(s) - \beta_S(s)\}) \quad (15)$$

Proof Fix $t > 0$, then from Equation (8) and (12) it holds, that:

$$\begin{aligned} P\{E_L(t, C_{ESS}) \leq \lambda\} &= 1 - P\{E_L(t, C_{ESS}) > \lambda\} \\ &= 1 - P\left\{ \inf_{0 \leq u \leq t-1} \left(\sup_{u \leq s \leq t-1} ([E_A(s, t) - E_S(s, t) - C_{ESS}, \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. E_A(u, t) - E_S(u, t) + C(u) - C_{ESS}]_+) \right) > \lambda \right\} \\ &= 1 - P\left\{ \inf_{0 \leq u \leq t-1} \left(\sup_{u \leq s \leq t-1} (E_A(s, t) - E_S(s, t) - C_{ESS}, \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. E_A(u, t) - E_S(u, t) + C(u) - C_{ESS}) \right) > \lambda \right\} \end{aligned}$$

Then the right-hand side of the probability can be bounded, using the representation of the actual storage capacity by the process $C(t) = C_{ESS} \forall t > 0$ and $C(t) = 0$ for $t = 0$ [7], as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda &< \inf_{0 \leq u \leq t-1} \left(\sup_{u \leq s \leq t-1} (E_A(s, t) - E_S(s, t) - C_{ESS}, E_A(u, t) - E_S(u, t) + C(u) - C_{ESS}) \right) \\ &\leq \sup_{0 \leq s \leq t-1} (E_A(s, t) - E_S(s, t) - C_{ESS}, E_A(0, t) - E_S(0, t) + C(0) - C_{ESS}) \\ &\leq \sup_{0 \leq s \leq t-1} (E_A(s, t) - E_S(s, t) - C_{ESS}) \\ &\leq \sup_{0 \leq s \leq t} \{E_A(s, t) + \alpha_A(t-s) - \alpha_A(t-s) + \beta_S(t-s) - \beta_S(t-s) - E_S(s, t) - C_{ESS}\} \\ &\leq \sup_{0 \leq s \leq t} (E_A(s, t) - \alpha_A(t-s)) + \sup_{0 \leq s \leq t} (\beta_S(t-s) - E_S(s, t)) \\ &\quad + \sup_{0 \leq s \leq t} (\alpha_A(s) - \beta_S(s)) - C_{ESS} \end{aligned}$$

By accounting for the Definition of the [Stochastic Energy Process](#):

$$P\left\{ \sup_{0 \leq s \leq t} \{(E_A(s, t) - \alpha_A(t-s))\} > x \right\} \leq \epsilon_A^u(x)$$

$$P\left\{ \sup_{0 \leq s \leq t} \{\beta_S(t-s) - E_S(s, t)\} > x \right\} \leq \epsilon_S^l(x)$$

and Equation (4) and the properties of the *(min, +)*-convolution it is proven, that:

$$\begin{aligned}
 P\{E_L(t, C_{ESS}) \leq \lambda\} &= 1 - P\left\{ \inf_{0 \leq u \leq t-1} \left(\sup_{u \leq s \leq t-1} (E_A(s, t) - E_S(s, t) - C_{ESS}, \right. \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \left. E_A(u, t) - E_S(u, t) + C(u) - C_{ESS}) \right) > \lambda \right\} \\
 &\geq 1 - \epsilon_A^u \otimes \epsilon_S^l (\lambda + C_{ESS} - \sup_{0 \leq s \leq t} \{\alpha_A(s) - \beta_S(s)\})
 \end{aligned}$$

Thereby the random processes $E_S(t)$ and $E_A(t)$ are not required to be necessarily independent random variables. \square

Guaranteed Temporal Service Probability

Definition 3 (Guaranteed Temporal Service Probability (GTSP)) *For a stochastic power queuing system, with a probabilistic upper bounded power demand process $E_A \sim \langle \epsilon_A^u, \alpha_A \rangle$ and a probabilistic lower bounded power supply process $E_S \sim \langle \epsilon_S^l, \beta_S \rangle$, the demand elasticity $E_T(t, C_{ESS})$ is bounded by:*

$$GTSP(t, C_{ESS}) = P\{E_T(t, C_{ESS}) \leq \tau\} \geq 1 - \epsilon_A^u \otimes \epsilon_S^l (C_{ESS} - \sup_{0 \leq s \leq t} \{\alpha_S(s) - \beta_S(s + \tau)\}) \quad (16)$$

Proof Fix $t > 0$, then from Equation (10 and (13) it holds, that:

$$\begin{aligned} P\{E_T(t, C_{ESS}) \leq \tau\} &= 1 - P\{E_T(t, C_{ESS}) > \tau\} \\ &\geq 1 - P\{E_A(t) - E_D(t + \tau) > 0\} \end{aligned}$$

Then the right-hand side of the probability can be bounded, using the representation of the actual storage capacity by the process $C(t) = C_{ESS} \forall t > 0$ and $C(t) = 0$ for $t = 0$ [7], as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &< E_A(t) - E_D(t + \tau) \\ &\leq E_A(t) - E_A(t + \tau) + E_L(t + \tau) \\ &\leq E_A(t) - E_A(t + \tau) + \inf_{0 \leq u \leq t + \tau - 1} \left(\sup_{u \leq s \leq t + \tau - 1} ([E_A(s, t + \tau) - E_S(s, t + \tau) - C_{ESS}, \right. \\ &\quad \left. E_A(u, t + \tau) - E_S(u, t + \tau) + C(u) - C_{ESS}]_+) \right) \\ &\leq E_A(t) - E_A(t + \tau) + \sup_{0 \leq s \leq t + \tau - 1} (E_A(s, t + \tau) - E_S(s, t + \tau) - C_{ESS}) \\ &\leq \sup_{0 \leq s \leq t + \tau} (E_A(t) - E_A(t + \tau) + E_A(s, t + \tau) - E_S(s, t + \tau)) - C_{ESS} \\ &\leq \sup_{0 \leq s \leq t + \tau} (E_A(t) - E_A(t + \tau) + E_A(t + \tau) - E_A(s) - E_S(s, t + \tau)) - C_{ESS} \\ &\leq \sup_{0 \leq s \leq t + \tau} (E_A(s, t) - E_S(s, t + \tau)) - C_{ESS} \\ &\leq \sup_{0 \leq s \leq t + \tau} \{E_A(s, t) + \alpha_A(t - s) - \alpha_A(t - s) + \beta_S(t + \tau - s) - \beta_S(t + \tau - s) - E_S(s, t + \tau) - C_{ESS}\} \\ &\leq \sup_{0 \leq s \leq t + \tau} (E_A(s, t) - \alpha_A(t - s)) + \sup_{0 \leq s \leq t + \tau} (\beta_S(t + \tau - s) - E_S(s, t + \tau)) \\ &\quad + \sup_{0 \leq s \leq t} (\alpha_A(s) - \beta_S(s + \tau)) - C_{ESS} \\ &\leq \sup_{0 \leq s \leq t} (E_A(t) - \alpha_A(t - s)) + \sup_{0 \leq s \leq t} (\beta_S(t + \tau - s) - E_S(s, t + \tau)) \\ &\quad + \sup_{0 \leq s \leq t} (\alpha_A(s) - \beta_S(s + \tau)) - C_{ESS} \end{aligned}$$

By accounting for the Definition of the [Stochastic Energy Process](#):

$$P\left\{ \sup_{0 \leq s \leq t} \{(E_A(s, t) - \alpha_A(t - s))\} > x \right\} \leq \epsilon_A^u(x)$$

$$P\left\{\sup_{0 \leq s \leq t} \{\beta_S(t-s) - E_S(s,t)\} > x\right\} \leq \epsilon_S^l(x)$$

and Equation (4) and the properties of the $(\min, +)$ -convolution its is proven, that:

$$\begin{aligned} P\{E_T(t, C_{ESS}) \leq \tau\} &\geq 1 - P\{E_A(t) - E_D(t+\tau) > 0\} \\ &\geq 1 - \epsilon_A^u \otimes \epsilon_S^l(C_{ESS} - \sup_{0 \leq s \leq t} (\alpha_A(s) - \beta_S(s+\tau))) \end{aligned}$$

Thereby the random processes $E_S(t)$ and $E_A(t)$ are not required to be necessarily independent random variables. \square

Optimization Algorithm

Algorithm 1 Optimization of the Quality of Service indicators for power system flexibility based on stochastic envelopes derived from multiple measurement traces.

Require:

indicators \leftarrow *GSCP, GPSP, GTSP*
processes^{*j*} \leftarrow *A^j, S^j*,
*envelope*_{*i*} \leftarrow $[(\rho \pm \delta) \cdot t \pm \sigma]_+$,
batteries \leftarrow *range(0, 50, 5)*
delays \leftarrow *range(0, 24, 1)*
*parameters*_{*i*} \leftarrow *combinations*(δ_i, σ_i)

Ensure:

bounds \leftarrow $p \cdot \exp^{-\beta \cdot x}$,
 $\alpha_A(T) - \beta_S(T) >$ *battery*,
E_S(t) *homogeneous*

for δ_i, σ_i **in** *parameters* **do**
 for *t* **in** *T* **do**
 for *j* **in** *processes* **do**
 rho \leftarrow $\sum_{t=1}^T E^i / T$
 if *upper envelope* **then**
 LHS^{*j,t*} \leftarrow $\sup_{0 \leq s \leq t} \{[(E_i(s, t) - (\rho + \delta) \cdot (t - s) + \sigma)]_+\}$
 else *lower envelope*
 LHS^{*j,t*} \leftarrow $\sup_{0 \leq s \leq t} \{[(\rho - \delta) \cdot (t - s) - \sigma - E_i(s, t)]_+\}$
 end if
 if *LHS*^{*j,t*} $<$ 0 **then**
 LHS^{*j,t*} \leftarrow 0
 end if
 end for
 end for
 β_i \leftarrow *Fit(LHS, exponential)*
 p_i \leftarrow *count(LHS[LHS > 0]) / count(LHS)*
end for

function CONVOLUTION(*p_i, β_i, x*)

$$p_{conv} \leftarrow \prod_i (p_i \cdot \beta_i \cdot \sum_i \frac{1}{\beta_i})^{\beta_i \cdot \sum_i \frac{1}{\beta_i}}$$

$$\beta_{conv} \leftarrow \frac{1}{\sum_i \beta_i}$$

return $p_{conv} \cdot \exp^{-\beta_{conv} \cdot x}$

end function

$\alpha_A \leftarrow [(E_A(t) - (\rho_A + \delta_A) \cdot t + \sigma_A)]_+$
 $\beta_S \leftarrow [(\rho_S - \delta_S) \cdot t - \sigma_S - E_S(t)]_+$

for *battery* **in** *batteries* **do**
 for *delay* **in** *delays* **do**
 for *indicator* **in** *indicators* **do**
 if *GSCP* **then**
 return 1 - Convolution(*p_i, β_i, battery* - $\gamma - \sup_{0 \leq s \leq T} \alpha_A(s) - \beta_S(s)$)
 else if *GPSP* **then**
 return 1 - Convolution(*p_i, β_i, λ + battery* - $\sup_{0 \leq s \leq T} \alpha_A(s) - \beta_S(s)$)
 else if *GTSP* **then**
 return 1 - Convolution(*p_i, β_i, battery* - $\sup_{0 \leq s \leq T} \alpha_A(s) - \beta_S(s + \tau)$)
 end if
 end for
 end for
end for

Description of the MILP

The MILP is build with the open-source framework PyPSA [24]. The objective function of the problem is an operational cost minimization [24] with perfect foresight and certain demand elasticity as an additional constraint. Since all marginal generation costs are set to zero, the problem optimizes the dispatch of the solar generation and the storage unit to fulfill the demand. In order to ensure the feasibility of the optimization, backup generation is available at high marginal costs. The input data used in the MILP approach is the same as for the SNC approach. The MILP is described in more detail in the following, while a full description of the PyPSA framework [24] is found at the corresponding web page (<https://pypsa.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>).

Variables and notation:

n	label of the buses
$t \in T$	label of the time point from the optimization horizon T
$s \in S$	label of the different generator, storage unit and demand types from the technologies S
$\tau \in \Delta$	label of the shifting time of the demand from the demand elasticity horizon Δ
$g_{n,s,t}$	dispatch of generator s at bus n at time t
$\bar{g}_{n,s}$	nominal power of generator s at bus n
$\bar{g}_{n,s,t}$ $\tilde{g}_{n,s,t}$	availability of generator s at bus n at time t per unit of nominal power
$h_{n,s,t}$	dispatch of storage unit s at bus n at time t
$f_{n,s,t}$	uptake of storage unit s at bus n at time t
$\bar{h}_{n,s}$	nominal power of the storage unit s at bus n
$soc_{n,s,t}$	state of charge of the storage unit s at bus n at time t
$r_{n,s}$	number of hours at nominal power to fill the state of charge
$o_{n,s}$	marginal cost of a storage, generator or demand for one MWh
$d_{n,s,t}$	exogenous demand s at bus n at time t
$d_{n,s,t}^*$	effective demand s at bus n at time t
$\bar{d}_{n,s}$	nominal power of demand s at bus n
$\delta_{n,s,t,\tilde{t}}$	shifted demand s at bus n at time t to time \tilde{t} per unit of nominal power
ρ	share of shifted exogenous demand
$\lambda_{n,t}$	shadow price of the constraint at bus n at time t
$c_{operational}$	operational costs

Objective: Minimization of operational costs

$$\min C_{operational} = \sum_{n,s} o_{n,s,t} g_{n,s,t} + \sum_{n,s} o_{n,s,t} h_{n,s,t}$$

Subject to:

Generator constraints: Generator nominal power and generator dispatch for each snapshot may be optimised.

$$\tilde{g}_{n,s,t} * \bar{g}_{n,s} \leq g_{n,s,t} \leq \bar{g}_{n,s,t} * \bar{g}_{n,s}$$

General storage unit constraints: Storage nominal power and dispatch for each snapshot may be optimised.

$$\begin{aligned} soc_{n,s,t} &= soc_{n,s,t-1} + f_{n,s,t} - h_{n,s,t} \\ 0 &\leq h_{n,s,t} \leq \bar{h}_{n,s} \\ 0 &\leq f_{n,s,t} \leq \bar{h}_{n,s} \\ 0 &\leq soc_{n,s,t} \leq r_{n,s} \bar{h}_{n,s} \end{aligned}$$

Additional storage unit constraints: Cyclic state of charge constraint with initially fully charged storage unit.

$$\begin{aligned} soc_{n,s,0} &= 1 \\ soc_{n,s,0} &= soc_{n,s,T} \end{aligned}$$

Demand constraints: Effective demands nominal power and dispatch for each timepoint τ in the demand elasticity horizon Δ may be optimised.

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &\leq d_{n,s,t}^* \leq \bar{d}_{n,s} \\ d_{n,s,t} + \sum_{\tau} (\delta_{n,s,t-\tau,t}^d - \delta_{n,s,t,t+\tau}^d) &= d_{n,s,t}^* \\ \sum_{\tau} \delta_{n,s,t+\tau}^d &\leq \rho d_{n,s,t} \end{aligned}$$

Nodal power balance: Nodal power balance at each bus n for each time t .

$$\sum_s g_{n,s,t} + \sum_s h_{n,s,t} - \sum_s f_{n,s,t} = \sum_s d_{n,s,t}^* \quad \leftrightarrow \quad \lambda_{n,t}$$